

Article**Urban Groundwater contamination from Onsite Wastewater Treatment Systems (OWTS) in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria****Peter Emmanuel Cooley^{1,2,3}**

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Abstract: Many studies have raised concern about the potential impact of onsite wastewater treatment systems (OWTS) on groundwater and their likely negative impacts on public health, but not many have been able to quantify the risks these systems pose to vulnerable groups, especially children. Therefore, the aim of this study was to quantify the public health risk of existing OWTS and input data into GIS to produce the public health risk map of the study area. The study involves the determination of groundwater concentrations of constituents of concerns, exposure concentration, routes of exposure and exposure population as well as calculating the risk estimates of nitrates and faecal coliform exposure. The results revealed that the risk of infection by faecal coliform organisms from ingestion of contaminated groundwater from drinking and beverage making as well as by accidental ingestion of contaminated groundwater while taking baths, by both children and adults, from the 45 percent of the sites had high intake of faecal coliform organisms that yielded risks exceeding 1×10^{-4} infection per year. The nitrates hazard quotients from ingestion of contaminated groundwater from OWTS by adults and children were all less than 1 in all the 20 investigated sites of the study area.

Keywords: Public Health, Decentralized Wastewater Treatment System, Risk Assessment, Septic Tank Systems, Onsite Wastewater Treatment System, Hazard Quotients and Toxicity

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1. Introduction

The impact of sewage contamination of urban groundwater from onsite wastewater treatment systems (OWTS) is increasingly recognized as a major threat to public health. It has been estimated that the total volume of wastewater disposed of via septic tanks is approximately 800 billion gallons per year (USEPA, 1977). Domestic septic tank effluents contain elevated concentrations of chlorides, sulfate, nitrate, ammonia, organic nitrogen, total nitrogen, total phosphate, total organic carbon (TOC), *faecal coliform* and *faecal streptococci* bacteria. Nutrients and pathogens are potential contaminants of subsurface and surface water if not properly treated prior to reaching the groundwater (Canter and Knox 1985). The major contaminant constituents in sludge from pit latrines and septic tanks are organic matter in the form of COD, nutrients and pathogens (bacteria, viruses and parasites) (Katukiza et al. 2012). Septic tank systems are responsible for contamination of water resources globally (Carroll et al. 2006). This is particularly precarious in developing countries where there is reliance on untreated groundwater supplies for domestic purposes. The OWTS risk assessment model is used to evaluate potential health risks to humans from exposure to wastewater effluent (Jones et al. 2000).

Treatment systems aim to reduce human exposure to pathogens and hazardous substance from faecal matter, thus risk assessment considerations are crucial (Siegrist et al. 2000, Stenstrom et al. 2011, WHO 2006) and must be factored into OWTS treatment goals to ensure public health, wellbeing and environmental protection (Siegrist et al., 2000). The OWTS risks assessment adopted from the concept of integrated risk assessment and management is based on the principles and practices of ecological risks assessment (USEPA 1998; Suter 1993; Jones 2001) and has the primary objective of estimating the potential impact of sewage hazard on human population (Paustenbach, 1989, 1995) with the capability to strengthen public health management strategies as well as improve risk-based decision-making (Beavers 1999) for effective public policy implementation (Cliver 2000; Geary 1992).

This paper focuses on the contamination of groundwater from faulty designed and constructed OWTS (septic tank systems) and the assessment of public health risk due to these systems using a modified framework developed by the United States National Academy of Science (NAS 1983), which provides a systematic OWTS risk assessment methodology (USEPA 1989, Kolluru et al. 1996, Jones et al. 2000) and using this result for suggestions of the improvement of public policies (Cookey 2013, Cookey et al 2014/2015). This model of public health risk assessment was based on the expanded framework of the white paper on integrated risk assessment/risk management included in a high-level risk assessment framework for OWTS (Jones et al. 2000). The latter is also one of the few studies that have adopted this model to conduct risk assessment of OWTS on groundwater, especially in developing countries like Nigeria. Therefore, the objective of this study was to apply this model to quantify the public health risks of OWTS on groundwater and its effects on the vulnerable population groups in the study area. The assumption of this study is that a standardized risk based assessment framework is needed for the formulation of effective public policies for regulation of OWTS in the study area. Hitherto, the design, screening and approval of OWTS is often based on the rule of thumb, vague and generalized environmental sanitation frameworks, which are heavily inadequate and maybe responsible for the negative impact of failed septic tanks on environmental quality. The major outcome of this work is the expectation that the result of this public health risk assessment (PHRA) can help influence relevant and responsible government agencies to formulate more suitable sanitation policies for the design, screening, construction, installation, operations and maintenance as well as for the approval process of OWTS (Cookey et al. 2015a).

2. Formulation of a methodology to evaluate public health risk linked to OWTS

2.1 General approach of evaluating public health risks

Risk is the likelihood that a course of action (or lack thereof) will result in an undesired event. According to Froese et al. (2009), risk is the probability of an adverse outcome, combined with the severity of the outcome. On the other hand, risk assessment is the activity that evaluate the toxic properties of a chemical or biological product and the conditions of, human exposure to this product in view to observing the reality of human exposure to this product and characterizing the nature of the effect that may result (NRC 1983, Emmanuel et al. 2009). The goal of this work was to describe how the chemical and microbial constituents of concern (stressors) reach humans (receptors) and cause systemic toxicity (nitrates) or microbial exposure to risk of infections (faecal coliforms) from wastewater in OWTS. This approach involves development of a conceptual site model, identification of chemical and microbial constituents of concern from wastewater to ascertain the potential of wastewater effluent to be released to the groundwater and determine the potential of health risks occurring at the study sites as a result of OWTS. In general, the steps for public health risk assessment for OWTS include (Figure 1): problem formulation, analysis and risk characterization (Jones et al. 2004).

Figure 1: Flowchart formulated for evaluation of public health risk of OWTS

2.2 Study site

The study was conducted at Port Harcourt city, the capital of Rivers State (Nigeria). The city is situated at the southern tip of the country, with a surface area of approximately 30,000 km², located along rivers and creeks, and partly on marshlands and mangrove swamps. The population of Port Harcourt city (within its municipal boundaries) was estimated to be about 800,000 in 2006 (GPHDMP 2008). Port Harcourt falls within the tropical rainforest belt, and is characterized by high rainfall, high temperature and high humidity all year round with an annual average rainfall of 4000 mm (GPHDMP 2008, NDRDMP 2001, PHWURSS 2009). The major regional aquifers in the study area are the Benin formation to the north and alluvium to the south. The groundwater levels vary from 0.3 to 6.9 m deep and are recharged directly by infiltration from rain (GPHDMP 2008, NDRDMP 2001, PHWURSS 2009). The municipal water system in the study site was designed and constructed during the colonial period of the early 1950s with very little maintenance and upgrading of the network since, despite the city's rapid expansion. This has resulted in a large section of the city not having any access to formal water supply. These areas generally obtain their water from private boreholes. Sanitation infrastructure is mainly provided by septic tanks, pit latrines, jetty toilets and direct flushing into the rivers.

2.3 Assessing stressors or constituents of concern

The public health risk component of this study focuses on primary constituents of concern (stressors) to humans in OWTS effluents: nitrogen containing compounds (nitrates) and microbial pathogens (faecal coliform organisms). The human properties evaluated as the result of exposure to nitrates in wastewater are systemic toxicity as defined by the USEPA. For a systemic (non-carcinogenic) endpoint, the dose for a Chemical of Concern (COC) to an exposed individual is estimated and compared to the human health toxicity value called reference dose (RfD). If the dose of the chemical of concern exceeds the RfD, the potential for adverse health effects exists (Jones et al. 2004; USEPA 1989). A hazard quotient value greater than 1.0 indicates that the threshold level of effects has been exceeded by the exposure concentration (USEPA 1989).

The contamination of groundwater by nitrate and its impact on human health have been the subject of many studies (Fraser and Chivers 1981; Laftouhi et al. 2003; Saadi and Maslouhi 2003; Ibnoussina et al. 2006). Ibnoussina et al. (2006) has shown that nitrates can be released easily into the groundwater in aquifers of sandy-low clay soil and very slow in soil types with a high clay content because of the ability of clayey soils to limit contaminants leaching into the groundwater (Swann 2008, Froese et al. 2009, Brown & Root 2001). Excess consumption of nitrates in the human diet can also lead to health risks that include methamoglobinaemia in infants (blue baby syndrome) and possible carcinogenic hazards in adults (OMS, 1996). Nitrates are a health concern and the WHO has set a guideline value of 50 mg/L NO_3^- as a safe level (11.3 mg/L as N).

The two human health properties commonly evaluated as a result of exposure to microbes originating from wastewater are infection and illness as defined in microbial risks assessment approaches (ILSI, 1996 and Haas et al, 1999). The microbial risks assessment endpoint to be adopted in this study is 'risk of infections'. The microbial risk of infection guideline is defined as greater than 1×10^{-4} (Macler and Regli, 1993). The pathogens of concern and indicator organisms for faecal contamination belong to several groups of microorganisms and they include enteric viruses, helminths (intestinal worms), bacteria, protozoa, and faecal streptococci together with *E. coli*. These are present in wastewater and biosolids contaminated with faecal matter (Feachem et al, 1983, Sidhu and Toze 2009). These organisms are responsible for a large number of gastro-intestinal tract infections such as typhoid fever, dysentery, diarrhoea and cholera. Human beings who are infected or carriers of diseases discharge pathogenic organisms to wastewater (Canter and Knox, 1985; Crites and Tchobanoglous, 1998). To make valid risk assessments in situations where there might be a significant probability of transmitting pathogens via water contaminated by wastewater, faecal coliforms are usually used as indicator organisms because they are easy to test and more numerous (Clesceri et al. 1999), although their presence may not directly indicate that other pathogens are present (Cardona, 1998). According to international regulations, faecal coliform organisms must not be detected in a sample of 100ml (OMS, 1996; European Commission, 1998).

3. Materials and methods

3.1 The general approach of evaluating public health risks assessment (PHRA)

The first stage in the implementation of the PHRA was the identification of relevant stakeholders required to participate in this project, the identification of areas of interest in the study area (Port Harcourt City, Rivers State, Nigeria) as well as development of the research framework flow chart. These were achieved with several consultations with the stakeholders. The selection of the relevant stakeholders resulted in the choice of OWTS and private groundwater borehole owners (households) and the regulatory community in the study area. The implication of this was the development of a residential performance audit survey questionnaire for OWTS (specific for homeowners/households) and public policy surveys questionnaire (regulatory community). This was done to provide situational field information that would support and validate the risk assessment and to determine the impact of the implementation of the existing relevant/related environmental sanitation policies and regulations on governance of the OWTS in the study area (Cookey et al 2014/2015). Also for effectiveness, the water sampling points and stakeholder consultations were influenced by the use of GPS as reflected in Figure 2

The key component of the public health risk assessment framework was the evaluation of exposure pathways and points where humans may come in contact with water containing constituents of concern from wastewater. The conceptual model focuses more on the residential area of the city of Port Harcourt (Figure 3). The exposure pathway generally falls into two categories onsite and offsite. Exposure pathways are points within the residences or the residential lots, whereas the offsite exposure points are the site boundaries (that is the edge of the residential lot) and the down-gradient of the OWTS where groundwater was collected from the study sites by water-cart-pushers and supplied to other families (Jones et al. 2004). The environmental media commonly evaluated are soil, surface water and groundwater, however, this work is mainly on privately owned domestic groundwater boreholes supply systems since its focuses only on the urban areas (in the rural areas it will be more on the hand dug wells, streams and rivers) (Cookey et al. 2008).

Figure 2: Water sampling points and stakeholder consultation mapped with the aid of GPS in Port Harcourt city (Rivers State, Nigeria)

3.2 Public health risks exposure pathways and exposure points

The potential for exposure to toxicants within the residence can only occur as the result of a system dysfunction. The study area's Conceptual Model of Public Health Risks Assessment associated with pathogens, chemicals and other nuisances of OWTS shows the graphic depiction of the pathways, media, stressors, receptors and ultimate targets considered in this assessment.

Figure 3: Conceptual Model of Public Health Risks Assessment of Onsite Wastewater Treatment Systems

The major types of OWTS identified in the study were septic systems; pour flush, ventilated pit latrines and the traditional pit latrines (this study is mainly on septic tank systems since it is an urban area). The diverse terminology used to describe septic system technologies includes: onsite wastewater treatment systems (OWTS), onsite sewage disposal systems (OSDS), wastewater infiltration systems and wastewater soil absorption system (WSAS) (Swann 2008, Siegrist et al. 2000). Swann (2008) categorized the septic systems into three basic groupings namely, conventional, alternative and innovative; while Siegrist et al. (2000) groups them also into three; traditional, contemporary and emerging. In the study area, the conventional and the traditional types constitute more than 80 percent of wastewater treatment systems (NISER 2010, Burubai et al 2007). The conventional onsite wastewater treatment systems design (septic tank systems) in Nigeria is the gravity fed systems, which involves a wastewater source (dwelling unit), tank-based treatment unit (made of sand-crete block – septic tank), and an infiltration unit (subsurface trench – soak-away pit) and some units are the outdated OWTS systems made up true disposal (non-treatment) systems such as straight pipes discharges (Siegrist et al. 2000, Fidelia 2004, Burubai et al 2007).

Also, the major exposure of pathogens and chemicals from these systems is due to total lack of maintenance of the systems by the owners, inadequate final disposal systems and a defective regulatory framework resulting in heavy contamination of the environmental media and subsequent exposure of the people to severe public health hazards. Field investigations revealed that most of the OWTS were actually releasing their contents into the environment because of various degrees of leakages, cracks, and damages of various parts of the systems. The study also revealed very serious poor structural conditions of OWTS. Other major sources of wastewater release into the environment are mostly from the household kitchens, laundry and bathrooms, which are channelled directly into the drainage systems or to the open area. Some households also channel the contents of their toilet systems directly into the drains, especially during the rains and other households located near the coastline channel their wastewater into the surface water (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Dysfunctional septic tank systems and typical systems setback to buildings, wells and boreholes in the city of Port Harcourt.

Note: (i) Septic tank system located in the old Port Harcourt township: A – drinking water borehole, B – broken septic tank releasing its contents and C – surface drain, (ii) System located in the Diobu and Mile 1-3 areas of the city: A – manhole of septic tank system, B – grey water from the bathroom and C – drinking water borehole. (iii) System located in the old Government Reserve Area of the city: A – Main house, B - shallow hand dug well, C – drinking water bore hole and D – septic tank system.

3.3 Risk analysis

This step focuses on tools and techniques used to measure or estimate exposure and risks. The exposure and effect issues identified during the problem formulation step are evaluated in more detail in the analysis step. The objective of this step is on quantitative methods (USEPA, 1989; Jones et al., 2004).

3.3.1 Determination of groundwater concentrations of constituents of concerns (COCs)

Physico-chemical and microbiological quality analysis of 20 selected groundwater boreholes in residential premises with septic tank systems were carried out. All samples were placed in sterile plastic containers with a volume of 2 litres and transported to laboratory within 24 hours for analysis. Duplicate groundwater samples were randomly collected from privately owned water boreholes from households that had OWTS as well as households that sold the water to water-cart-pushers who in turn supplied other households.

The Standard Methods for Examination of Water and Wastewater (APHA, AWWA, & WEF 2005) were used for analysing the parameters measured. The parameters analysed were turbidity, pH, total dissolved solids, conductivity, hardness, nitrate, phosphate, sulphate, chloride, iron, lead, zinc, heterotrophic bacteria counts, and total and faecal coliform counts. The result of the groundwater analysis was subjected to one-way ANOVA to determine their levels of confidence. The groundwater boreholes and the OWTS locations were determined using a GPS device. A tape rule was used in measuring the distance between the OWTS and groundwater boreholes. These data and the results of the risk analysis were imputed into GIS software to produce a public risk map of OWTS in the study area.

3.3.2 Determination of exposure concentration, routes of exposure and exposure population

For adverse impact to human health to occur, a potentially exposed population is required at the exposure point. The potential receptors include residents, visitor's onsite and offsite residents and visitors who make use of the water supplied from the impacted sites as well as other water facilities at the site boundaries which may also be impacted by OWTS (Figure 3). The subgroups of the receptors may also include children, adults, old people and other sensitive subpopulations such as the immune-compromised individuals. For this study, our focus was on children and adults with the routes of exposure for potential receptors covering ingestion and dermal contact. For each exposure route, an exposure model is constructed and applied to estimate a daily intake for the wastewater constituents of concern. Also, separate daily intakes were used for children and adults due to differences in exposure factors such as body weight, ingestion rate and exposure frequencies. Daily intakes represent the estimated dose of the constituents of concern. The estimated doses (Table 1) are compared to health toxicity values or guideline values to determine if adverse health impacts are predicted and the level of their effect (RAIS, 2003).

3.4 Risk characterization: calculating risk estimates for nitrates and faecal coliform exposure

The risk characterization process evaluated the exposure and effects data developed in the analysis step while producing estimates of risk (Jones et al, 2004). Risks characterization (Table 1) serves as the link between risk assessment and risk management (USEPA, 1989).

The public health risk assessment is used to evaluate exposure to nitrates and pathogens. The public health endpoint evaluated for nitrates is systemic toxicity and probability of infection for faecal coliform. Values greater than 1.0 indicate that the threshold level for effects has been exceeded by the exposure concentration (USEPA, 1989; Jones et al. 2004). The microbial risks assessment endpoint adopted in this study is risk of infections. To quantify risks of infection from microbial exposure, the measured faecal coliforms in groundwater samples were assumed to be *E.coli* greater than 1×10^4 (Macler and Regli 1993).

Table 1: Estimation formulae of exposure concentration, routes, and populations

Intake	Estimation Formulae	Constituents of Concern
<i>Estimation of constituents of concern ingestion of groundwater by drinking and beverage by adult and child</i>		
Intake (mg/kg.day)	$CW \times IR \times EF \times ED/BW \times AT$	Nitrates
Intake (mg/kg-day)	$CW \text{ (cfu)} \times IR \times EF \times ED/BW \times AT$	Feecal coliform
<i>Estimation of constituents of concern by accidental ingestion of groundwater by adult and child while taking baths</i>		
Intake (mg/kg.day)	$CW \times CR \times EF \times ET \times ED/BW \times AT$	Nitrates
Intake (mg/kg.day)	$CW \text{ (cfu)} \times CR \times EF \times ET \times ED/BW \times AT$	Feecal coli-form
<i>Estimation of constituents of concern by dermal contact with groundwater while taking baths by adult and child</i>		
Intake (mg/kg.day)	$CW \times CF \times PC \times SA \times ET \times EF \times ED/BW \times AT$	Nitrates
Intake (mg/kg.day)	$CW \text{ (cfu)} \times CF \times PC \times SA \times ET \times EF \times ED/BW \times AT$	Feecal coli-form
Variable	Value used	Explanation/Source
CW = Concentration in water Sample	Chemical-specific (mg/L) Organism-specific (cfu)	Concentration is obtained from sample data
CF = Conversion factor	$m/100cm \times 1000 L/m^3$	Regional IV Supplemental Guidance to RAGS (USEPA, 1995)
SA = Available surface area	1.94 m ²	Average total body surface area for an adult (Dermal Exposure Assessment, USEPA, 1992)
	1.07 m ²	Average total body surface area for a child (USEPA, 1992)
PC = Permeability constant	Chemical-specific (0.001cm/hour)-Nitrate	Dermal Exposure Assessment, (USEPA, 1992)
IR = Ingestion rate	2L/day adult; 1 L/day child	USEPA 1989; OSWER Directive (USEPA 1991a/b)
EF = Exposure frequency	350 days/year	OSWER Directive (USEPA 1991a/b)
	45days/year	OSWER Directive (USEPA 1991a/b)
ED = Exposure duration	30 years- adult; 6years-child	Residential exposure for a 30-year duration (OSWER Directive , USEPA 1991a/b)
ET = Exposure time	1 hour/day	Dermal Exposure Assessment, (USEPA, 1992)
BW = Body weight	70 kg-adult; 15kg-child	Adult (USEPA, 1991a/b)
AT = Averaging time	365 days/year x ED	Averaging time for non-carcinogens (USEPA, 1989, 1991a/b)
	365 days/year x 70years	Averaging time for non-carcinogens (USEPA, 1989, 1991a/b)

$$\text{Non-cancer hazard quotient} = E/RfD \quad (I)$$

Where: E = exposure level (intake of nitrates in Table 1)

RfD = Reference dose (1.6 mg/kg-d) value for nitrate (USEPA, 2002a; RAIS, 2003)

The beta-Poisson dose-response model was used to estimate the risk or probability of infection from ingestion and/or contact with groundwater contaminated by OWTS (Haas et al. 1999).

$$P = 1 - (1 + (N/\beta))^{-\alpha} \quad (II)$$

Where: P = Probability of infection

N = Microbial exposure (Faecal coliform in Table 1)

β and α = Dose response curve specific to an individual microorganism

(dose response curve for *E. coli* indicates $\beta = 1.61 \times 10^6$ and $\alpha = 0.1705$; Pepper et al., 1996).

A correlation analysis was also carried out to establish the degree of the relationship between risk of infection and the distance of OWTS to groundwater boreholes in the study sites. The results of this analysis were subjected to a single factor anova test and it gave 98 percent confidence level, which showed that the data were normally distributed.

4.0 Results

4.1. Physico-chemical and bacteriological quality of groundwater

Physico-chemical parameters were analysed for twenty water samples collected from private boreholes in the study area. The result of physicochemical characteristics of the groundwater quality are summarised in Table 2. In general, the following parameters were in compliance with the Nigerian and WHO Standards for Drinking Water Quality: turbidity, conductivity, nitrates, phosphates, iron, lead and zinc. The nitrate concentrations of the groundwater in all the 20 sites were below the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Nigerian Drinking Water Quality recommended standards. The pH of the samples studied varied from 5 to 6, depicting an acidic water quality. Acidic waters are of concern because of their corrosive characteristic (Sawyer, et al, 2003).

The results of heterotrophic bacteria counts, total and faecal coliform bacteria are presented in Table 3. Table 3 shows that 45 percent of the groundwater samples were contaminated with faecal coliform organisms, while 55 percent of groundwater sampled were free from microbial contamination. In the case of faecal coliform bacterial counts, the minimum values ranged from 0 to 1100CFUL/100ml. The result of the microbiological quality of the water samples showed high contamination levels were common in boreholes that were below 8 meters safe distance from the septic tank systems in the study area.

Characterization of human health risks

4.4.1 Microbiological and chemical quantification of exposure

The estimation of the faecal coliform organism's intakes from ingestion of water by drinking, beverages and accidental ingestion shows that the volumes drunk do not vary from site to site, only the water quality. Therefore, these observations are obvious in both the child and adult risks (Table 4). The result also showed that the children tend to take in more pathogenic

organisms than the adults per kg weight. On the other hand, the presence of nitrates with relations to intake by ingestion through drinking and beverages-making was well distributed in all the 20 water samples taken, though it was of very low concentration.

Table 2: Physico-chemical characteristics of groundwater boreholes in Port Harcourt city

Parameters	Unit	No of Samples	Average	Minimum	Maximum	Variance
Turbidity	mg/l	20	0.052	0.040	0.100	0.000396
pH	U	20	5.902	5.590	6.580	0.076096
TDS	mg/l	20	298.550	20.000	3750.000	713917.8
Conductivity	µS/cm	20	106.203	7.000	1330.500	84239
Hardness	mg/l	20	34.716	2.400	417.020	8321.671
Nitrate	mg/l	20	4.996	0.390	8.170	5.43831
Phosphorous	mg/l	20	0.016	0.010	0.100	0.000416
Sulphates	mg/l	20	19.489	0.690	130.380	843.5877
Chloride	mg/l	20	63.810	7.000	900.000	39061.08
Iron	mg/l	20	0.024	0.002	0.175	0.001399
Lead	mg/l	20	0.002	0.001	0.003	3.58E-07
Zinc	mg/l	20	0.054	0.013	0.345	0.00506

Table 3: Microbiological quality of groundwater boreholes in Port Harcourt city

Groundwater boreholes sampling sites	Distance from OWTS (m)	Total heterotrophic bacteria counts	Total Coliform counts	Faecal Coliform counts
		cfu/100ml	cfu/100ml	cfu/100ml
1	4.2	1.62x10 ³	≥2400	1100
2	19	5.4x10 ²	4	0
3	70	4.0 x 10 ¹	23	0
4	10	1.1 x 10 ²	4	0
5	8.5	4.0x10 ¹	4	0
6	15	8.0 x 10 ¹	0	0
7	7	1.5x10 ²	1100	150
8	4.8	5.7 x 10 ²	240	43
9	20	7.0 x 10 ¹	0	0
10	8	3.2 x 10 ²	0	0
11	9	4.0x10 ²	4	0
12	5	3.9 x 10 ²	≤2400	150
13	15	7.0 x 10 ¹	4	0
14	6	4.5 x 10 ²	150	7
15	7.1	1.4 x 10 ³	75	43
16	3	1.83 x 10 ³	≥2400	75
17	4.6	3.8 x 10 ²	150	75
18	11	1.2 x 10 ¹	9	0
19	6	4.0 x 10 ¹	43	23
20	15	4.0 x 10 ¹	4	0

However, faecal coliform organisms did not show much intake differentials in quantity among children and adults in the study area. There was nevertheless a very marked difference between both groups from nitrate contamination. Dermal contact with nitrate contaminated water while taking baths with both child and adult was more or less at the same level.

4.4.2 Microbiological quantification of risk of infection

Table 4 presents the microbial risk characterization. The risk of infection by faecal coliform organisms from ingestion of contaminated groundwater from drinking and beverage-making and accidental ingestion of contaminated groundwater while taking baths by both children and adults shows that 45 percent of the sites with a high intake of faecal coliform organisms yielded a risk level exceeding 1×10^{-4} infection per year (1 person per 10,000). This is considered as an intolerable risk level for drinking water supplies in the United States (Hass, 1996; Kolluru et al. 1996, USEPA 1999, 2002b).

There was a direct correlation ($r=0.99$) between risk of infection and distance of OWTS to boreholes by ingestion of contaminated groundwater from drinking and beverage-making for a child and for an adult ($r=0.86$). There was also a direct correlation ($r=0.91$) between risk of infection and distance of OWTS to borehole for an accidental ingestion of contaminated groundwater while taking a bath by a child or an adult ($r=0.91$). A case-control study of septic tank density and diarrhoea found a risk of illness six times greater in children (aged 1 to <19 years) drinking from *Enterococci* contaminated wells in the US (Borchardt et al, 2003).

4.4.2 Quantification of nitrate risk

The nitrates hazard quotients at the time studied were all below the RfD of 1.6mg/kg.d in all the sites for direct ingestion of water through drinking and beverages-making, accidental ingestion while taking a bath or dermal contact while bathing. The nitrate hazard quotient from ingestion of contaminated groundwater from OWTS by adults and children was less than 1 in all the 20 sites of the study area (Table 6 and Figure 8). Though the value was very low, children tended to be also more at risk of systemic toxicity than the adults. Nitrate was not a major health concern from this study (Table 5).

5. Discussion and Conclusion

This public health risk assessment (PHRA) focused mainly on the characterised risks for nitrates and faecal coliform organisms from OWTS. The PHRA also estimated risks for complete exposure pathways and quantified the risks for the adults and children population in the study area. The result showed that 45 percent of the groundwater supply sources in the study area were highly contaminated with faecal coliform organisms from the on-site wastewater treatment systems, i.e. septic systems (Table 3). This study is in agreement with several other studies which confirmed cases of microbiological contamination of water sources as results of failing OWTS (Carroll 2005, Carroll et al. 2006, Fliesher et al. 1998, Borchardt et al. 2003) as well as with other similar studies conducted in Nigeria: Adetunji et al. (2011) showed that all wells of the Agbowo community of Ibadan (Nigeria) were contaminated with coliform micro-organisms. Adekunle (2008), Fasunwon et al. (2008), Oparaocha et al. (2008) and Adelekan, (2010), Ifabiyi (2008) and Akinbile and Yusoff (2011) also recorded higher values of coliform counts in various groundwater wells That were not in compliance with WHO (2008), USEPA (2009), OMS (1996) and European Commission (1998) guidelines which state that *E. coli* must not be detectable in any 100 mL of water meant for drinking or for treated water entering distribution systems.

Table 5: Nitrates ingestion of contaminated groundwater from OWTs in Port Harcourt city

Sample sites	OWTS setbacks to groundwater boreholes (meters)	Measured conc (mg/l)	Ingestion of contaminated groundwater from drinking and beverage making				Accidental ingestion of contaminated groundwater while taking baths				Dermal contact of contaminated groundwater while taking baths			
			Intake dose (mg/kg.day) adult	Intake dose (mg/kg.day) child	Hazard quotient (mg/kg.day) adult	Hazard quotient (mg/kg.day) child	Intake dose (mg/kg.day) adult	Intake dose (mg/kg.day) child	Hazard quotient (mg/kg.day) adult	Hazard quotient (mg/kg.day) child	Intake dose (mg/kg.day) adult	Intake dose (mg/kg.day) child	Hazard quotient (mg/kg.day) adult	Hazard quotient (mg/kg.day) child
1	4.2	4.41	0.12	0.28	7.5×10^{-2}	1.8×10^{-1}	3.02×10^{-3}	0.01	1.9×10^{-3}	4.1×10^{-3}	1.51×10^{-4}	0.0002	9.4×10^{-5}	1×10^{-4}
2	19	7.11	0.19	0.45	1.2×10^{-1}	2.8×10^{-1}	4.87×10^{-3}	0.01	3.0×10^{-3}	7.1×10^{-3}	2.43×10^{-4}	0.00025	1.5×10^{-4}	1.6×10^{-4}
3	70	1.32	0.04	0.08	2.3×10^{-2}	5.3×10^{-2}	9.04×10^{-4}	0.002	5.7×10^{-3}	1.3×10^{-3}	4.51×10^{-5}	0.00001	2.8×10^{-4}	2.9×10^{-5}
4	10	8.17	0.22	0.52	1.4×10^{-1}	3.3×10^{-1}	5.60×10^{-3}	0.013	3.5×10^{-4}	8.1×10^{-3}	2.79×10^{-4}	0.00029	1.7×10^{-4}	1.8×10^{-4}
5	8.5	5.41	0.15	0.35	9.3×10^{-2}	2.2×10^{-1}	3.71×10^{-3}	0.009	2.3×10^{-3}	5.4×10^{-3}	1.85×10^{-4}	0.00019	1.12×10^{-5}	1.2×10^{-4}
6	15	7.06	0.19	0.45	1.2×10^{-1}	2.8×10^{-1}	4.84×10^{-3}	0.01	3.0×10^{-3}	7.1×10^{-3}	2.41×10^{-4}	0.00025	1.5×10^{-4}	1.6×10^{-4}
7	7	0.99	0.03	0.07	1.7×10^{-2}	3.9×10^{-2}	6.78×10^{-4}	0.002	4.2×10^{-3}	1.0×10^{-3}	3.38×10^{-5}	0.00001	2.1×10^{-5}	2.2×10^{-5}
8	4.8	6.84	0.18	0.44	1.2×10^{-1}	2.8×10^{-1}	4.68×10^{-3}	0.011	2.9×10^{-3}	6.8×10^{-3}	2.34×10^{-4}	0.00024	1.5×10^{-4}	1.9×10^{-4}
9	20	7.46	0.20	0.48	1.3×10^{-1}	2.98×10^{-1}	5.11×10^{-3}	0.012	3.2×10^{-3}	7.4×10^{-3}	2.55×10^{-4}	0.00026	1.6×10^{-4}	1.6×10^{-4}
10	8	3.49	0.10	0.22	6×10^{-2}	1.4×10^{-1}	2.39×10^{-3}	0.006	1.5×10^{-3}	3.5×10^{-3}	1.19×10^{-4}	0.00012	7.4×10^{-5}	1.6×10^{-4}
11	9	4.68	0.13	0.30	8×10^{-2}	1.9×10^{-1}	3.205×10^{-3}	0.008	2.0×10^{-3}	4.7×10^{-3}	1.60×10^{-4}	0.00016	1×10^{-4}	1×10^{-4}
12	5	5.23	0.14	0.33	8.9×10^{-2}	2.1×10^{-1}	3.58×10^{-3}	0.008	2.2×10^{-3}	5.3×10^{-3}	1.79×10^{-4}	0.00018	1.1×10^{-4}	1.1×10^{-4}
13	15	2.29	0.06	0.15	3.9×10^{-2}	9.1×10^{-2}	1.57×10^{-3}	0.004	9.8×10^{-3}	2.3×10^{-3}	7.82×10^{-5}	0.00008	4.95×10^{-5}	5×10^{-5}
14	6	4.33	0.12	0.28	7.4×10^{-2}	1.7×10^{-1}	2.97×10^{-3}	0.007	1.9×10^{-3}	4.3×10^{-3}	1.48×10^{-4}	0.00015	9.3×10^{-5}	9.4×10^{-5}
15	7.1	7.77	0.21	0.50	1.3×10^{-1}	3.1×10^{-1}	5.32×10^{-3}	0.012	3.3×10^{-3}	7.6×10^{-3}	2.65×10^{-4}	0.00027	1.7×10^{-4}	1.8×10^{-4}
16	3	7.02	0.19	0.45	1.2×10^{-1}	2.8×10^{-1}	4.81×10^{-3}	0.011	3.0×10^{-3}	7.0×10^{-3}	2.40×10^{-4}	0.00025	1.5×10^{-4}	1.6×10^{-4}
17	4.6	6.18	0.17	0.40	1.1×10^{-1}	2.5×10^{-1}	4.23×10^{-3}	0.010	2.6×10^{-3}	6.2×10^{-3}	2.11×10^{-4}	0.00022	1.3×10^{-4}	1.4×10^{-4}
18	11	5.30	0.15	0.34	9.1×10^{-2}	2.1×10^{-1}	3.63×10^{-3}	0.009	2.3×10^{-3}	5.3×10^{-3}	1.81×10^{-4}	0.00019	1.1×10^{-4}	1.2×10^{-4}
19	6	0.39	0.01	0.03	6.88×10^{-3}	1.6×10^{-2}	2.67×10^{-3}	0.001	1.7×10^{-3}	3.8×10^{-3}	1.33×10^{-5}	0.00001	8.3×10^{-4}	8.8×10^{-6}
20	15	4.46	0.12	0.29	7.6×10^{-2}	1.8×10^{-1}	3.05×10^{-3}	0.007	1.9×10^{-3}	4.4×10^{-3}	1.52×10^{-4}	0.00016	9.5×10^{-4}	1×10^{-4}

The deterioration of the quality of groundwater and surface water resources is attributed to contamination from organic matter, micro-pollutants, nutrients and pathogens (Clara et al. 2003, Foppen 2002, Nakagawa et al. 2000, Nyenje et al. 2010, Styen et al. 2004). The microbiological quality of the water samples (Table 3) showed that those with faecal coliform contamination levels were common with boreholes that were below 8 meters safe distance from the septic tank systems in the study area and from a distance of 8 m or above no trace of faecal coliform organisms were found in the water samples. This is in agreement with the minimum standard distance of 15.24 meters set by the USEPA/US-HUD/FHA, Canadian, and UK governments (InspectAPedia 2010). Therefore, it is important for issues of setback of OWTS to groundwater of OWTS in particular locations/zones to be adequately recognized for environmental and public health protection of groundwater sources from the siting of OWTS. The study revealed that the relevant legal frameworks adopted in the study area were silent on the stipulation of appropriate setback between the OWTS and the groundwater sources and this may be responsible for the inconsistencies observed in the measured setbacks of the case study area. We propose that appropriate setback distance between the OWTS and nearby water resources should be included in the legal framework for regulation of OWTS.

To have safe drinking water, treatment technology needs to be applied that can achieve 99 to 99.99 percent removal/inactivation because of the need to protect potentially exposed persons as well as reduce risk of infection to 1×10^{-4} per year from water consumption. The results also show that children were more at risk than adults. This result was in agreement with Strauss et al. (2001), in a Canadian study of rural households using well water, which showed that a child, less than 10 years has a greater chance of having an episode of gastrointestinal illness given the presence of at least 5 colony-forming units of *E. coli* in the water, which is 4.2 (95% confidence interval) times higher than that for adults older than 50 years. According to Rogan and Brady (2009), children are likely to be more susceptible to water-borne illnesses than adults because they drink relatively more water, develop gastroenteritis more often, and become dehydrated more quickly when they develop gastrointestinal illnesses. Thus, the fact that adults can consume the water without incident is not a guarantee that the child can do so.

Nitrate values ranged from 0.39 mg/l to 8.17mg/l (Table 5). These values are in compliance with the USEPA maximum contaminant level of nitrate-nitrogen concentration of 10mg/l. The low level of nitrates in all the samples may be due to a low pH (5.6-6.6) of all the samples in the study sites and high clayey properties of the Benin Formation aquifer (GPHDMP, 2007). This condition is conducive to create anaerobic conditions, which play a very important role in the denitrification process. This is in agreement with Gerritse et al. (1995), who concluded that denitrification was a likely cause of nitrate disappearance from the Darling Plateau, a Western Australian septic tank system. The authors argued that pH (6.1-7.7), low temperature and the changing water table above the lateritic layer were conducive to create the anaerobic conditions ideal for the denitrification process. Where the groundwater is anaerobic, nitrates will be reduced to nitrogen gas (Lawrence et al. 2001). For example, in some peri-urban areas of Dhaka (Bangladesh), it has been noted that groundwater nitrate concentrations are low despite the heavy nitrogen pollution from poor onsite sanitation (Gerritse et al. 1995; Lawrence et al. 2001; Ward et al. 2005).

The main purpose of the Public Health Risks Map developed in this study was to indicate areas that are at risk as a result of the use of OWTS for sewage treatment and management in the study area (Figure 5). The outcome of the risk map showed how widespread and disperse the risk of the use of septic tank systems is in the study area, especially in the area of design and siting of OWTS. This is in agreement with Carroll et al. (2006), who developed a risk map to identify risks at Gold Coast (Australia) by the use of OWTS for the purpose of creating an opportunity for effective development of appropriate management options to mitigate the identified risks as well as to identify areas that should not have the density of septic systems increased or where appropriate assessment needs to be implemented to ascertain the most suitable decentralized wastewater treatment system. The risk map also indirectly brought up the issue of OWTS density, which is septic tanks quantity located in an area (tanks per square mile). Although, this was not the focus of this study, experts believe that density of OWTS has the potential to impact negatively on groundwater quality (Perkins 1984, Yates 1985, Carroll 2005, Swam 2008). The USEPA suggested that areas with >40 septic

tanks/hectare are those with the greatest potential for groundwater contamination (USEPA 1977, Pradhan et al 2007). Also, the development of the risk map has two implications: (I) is the identification of 'at risk' areas as this will create opportunity for effective development of appropriate management options to mitigate the identified risks (II) identify areas that should not more septic systems or where appropriate assessment are required to determine type and implementation of suitable decentralized wastewater treatment system.

Figure 5: Public Health Risks Map of Port Harcourt City

The findings of this study were also in agreement with Butler et al. (1995), Carroll et al., (2006) and Brown and Root, (2001) in their study where they categorized the most common septic tank problems to include: cracks, deterioration and damage of various degrees, leakages and exposing the contents to the environment as well as high rate of system failure which often result to discharging of raw sewage into the environment, poor structural conditions, water infiltration into the system, ponding of the system, presence of sludge around the distribution system and clogging of the absorption fields. Other OWTS challenges include: the high failure rate of septic systems are often associated with inappropriate location of systems in areas with inadequate separation distance to groundwater sources, insufficient absorption area, improper design or installation and poorly maintained and operated systems as well as absence of effective legislative and regulatory framework for sustainable management of OWTS. This was seen to be responsible for the lack of improvement of treatment technology that would have ensured effective wastewater management systems in the study area.

In concluding, defective design, constructed and operated OWTS were observed to be responsible for the contamination of groundwater sources by faecal coliform organisms in the study area. There was also a direct correlation between the risk of infection to the distance of setbacks of the OWTS to the groundwater sources which implies that future sanitation legal framework should take a critical look at the issue of setbacks as well as system densities. It was interesting to note that children tended to take in more pathogenic organisms than adults, and the risks of infection were seen to be higher amongst the children than the adults. The nitrate concentration was not a risk factor in the study area both in the case of intakes and hazard quotients because the value obtained from the risk analysis and characterization were well below the reference dose (RfD). Further studies are needed for better understanding of the comprehensive nature of the risks the OWTS pose to the city of Port Harcourt, Nigeria and other cities

in the country. Going forward will require an expanded scope of the current study of risks assessment to include soil and surface water, engineering, ecological and socio-economic risks assessment of onsite wastewater treatment systems in the study area.

The uncertainty surrounding the quantification of risk estimates in this study is the fact that the assumption used in the risks assessment may not be able to really ascertain the real risks because the estimation was based on the data and models adapted from developed countries like United States of America, which do not have the same climatic conditions as the case study area and have improved access to potable water supplies, better sanitation systems (even if it was an OWTS) and strong and enforceable sanitation regulatory framework. Therefore, the degree of the risks may be under estimated, but this does not diminish the importance and relevance of this work.

This work shows an urgent need to improve the public water supply systems so that homeowners and the people do not resort to providing their own water supply by directly accessing the shallow polluted groundwater in their vicinities. Also, the health officers should take the job of monitoring and enforcement of existing (though inadequate) legislative and regulatory standards serious. The Nigerian Standards Organizations and relevant health and environmental authorities should come up with well-defined regulatory and standards frameworks that will drive improved technology selection and ensure sustainable OWTS.

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